

PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS AND THEIR ROLE IN LITERATURE

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Annotation: *The study of phraseological units, in our opinion, is one of the topical issues for the younger generation, in addition, knowledge of phraseological units and the ability to use phraseological units make our speech interesting, emotional, figurative.*

It should also be noted that in our age of computer technology and communication through iPhones and iPads, children have become much less likely to read. But how much wisdom in children's fiction! How many phraseological turns exist that accurately reflect the state of a person, the situation in which he finds himself, his mood and character.

Key words: *Phraseological units, literary text, communication.*

In modern linguistics, there is no consensus on the issue of the essence and definition of phraseological units as a linguistic unit. There are theoretical disagreements about the scope of phraseology and the nature of linguistic facts interpreted as phraseological units. The importance of an accurate definition of phraseological turnover is evidenced by lexicographic practice, when ordinary phrases are given as

phraseological units in dictionaries (feeling of the elbow, military operations, seize hands, for nothing, etc.) and words (on the move, in general, no, no, on hand, on ointment, etc.).

The definition of the general nature of phraseology was given by Sh. Bally: "combinations that have firmly entered the language are called phraseological turns." Researchers V.L. Arkhangelsky, S.G. Gavrin, V.N.

Teliya define phraseology as a linguistic unit, which is characterized by such secondary features as metaphor, equivalence and synonymy with a word. V.V. Vinogradov put forward as the most essential feature of phraseological turnover its equivalence and synonymy with the word. Teliya V.N. Primary tasks and methodological problems of the study of the phraseological composition of the language in the context of culture // *Phraseology in the context of culture*. - M., 1999. - S. 13. But, according to N.M. Shansky, metaphor is also inherent in many words, and equivalence - not in all stable combinations. Therefore, the inclusion of these secondary and dependent features in the definition of a phraseological unit is not entirely correct. The scientist emphasized that "the correct definition of a phraseological unit is impossible without taking into account its differences from the word and free combination." In his work "Phraseology of the Modern Russian Language", Shansky gives the following definition: "Phraseological

turnover is a language unit reproduced in finished form, consisting of two or more stressed components of a verbal character, fixed (i.e. constant) in its meaning, composition and structure." The linguist believes that the main property of phraseological turnover is its reproducibility, since "phraseological units are not created in the process of communication, but are reproduced as ready-made integral units." So, the phraseological units "to distant lands", "the trail is cold", "there is nothing to cover", etc. are extracted from memory in their entirety.

Phraseologisms are significant linguistic units, which are characterized by their own meaning, independent of the meanings of their constituent components. Phraseological turnover consists of the same components, located one after another in a strictly established order. In some phraseological turns, a different arrangement of components is noted: burn with shame - burn with shame, pull the bagpipe - pull the bagpipe, however, in such phraseological units, the location of the words that form them is fixed in

two equally possible variant forms.

Phraseologisms are distinguished by the impenetrability of the structure.

The bulk of phraseological units act as integral language units, insertion into which is usually impossible (from young to old, in the prime of life, in seventh heaven, it's in the bag, etc.). In some phraseological units, the components are separated by a distance ("You literally can't see anything", "What a scolding dad gave him today!").

N.M. Shansky considered the differences between phraseological units and free phrases. Phraseological turns are distinguished by reproducibility, integrity of meaning, stability of composition and structure, and, as a rule, impenetrability of the structure. The differences between phraseological turns and words, as the scientist believed, are as follows: words consist of elementary meaningful units of the language, morphemes, and phraseological units - from components of a verbal character, words act as grammatically uniform formations, and phraseological units are grammatically separate

formations. Thus, phraseological units have "a characteristic set of differential features:

1) these are ready-made language units that are not created in the process of communication, but are retrieved from memory as a whole;

2) these are linguistic units, which are characterized by constancy in meaning, composition and structure (similar to individual words);

3) in accentological terms, these are sound complexes in which their constituent components have two (or more) main stresses;

4) these are segmented formations, the components of which are perceived by the speakers as words. Shansky N.M. *Phraseology of the modern Russian language* / N.M. Shansky. - M.: Higher School, 1985. - p. 29.

Phraseologisms must have the entire set of these features that distinguish them from free combinations and words.

In the language of every nation there are stable figurative phrases that are reproduced in speech like a word, and are not built like phrases and sentences. Such turns are called

phraseological units. Another important property of phraseological units: the meaning of a whole phraseological unit does not consist of the meanings of the words included in it, for example, the expression *ate a dog*, which means to be a master in some business, is completely unrelated to the meaning of the words included in it.

Phraseologisms differ in the degree of cohesion of the components. If it is maximum, then these are phraseological fusions, for example, *to get into a mess*, *beat the thumbs*, *without hesitation*. If the connection between the components is smaller, these are phraseological units (*pull the strap*, *lather the neck*). In phraseological combinations, one member of a phraseological unit has the so-called limited, associated use, and the second is free: *a sensitive issue*, *fraught with consequences*, *pitch darkness*.

The sources of phraseological units of the Russian language are diverse.

The main part of the phraseological units of the Russian language is of primordially Russian origin, their

source is, for example, professional speech (*sharpen lyasy*, *beat backhands*, *without a hitch*, *remove shavings*, *run aground*, *play first violin*). Some got into the literary language from jargon (*rubbing glasses*, *a bit card*, *going all-in - with gamblers*) and colloquial speech. Some phraseological units came from dialects and are associated with the labor of the peasantry (*to turn the shafts*, *from a bag into a matting*, *it is written on the water with a pitchfork*). Many phraseological units have their source in liturgical books (*the holy of holies*, *the fiend of hell*, *in the image and likeness*, *the voice of one crying in the wilderness*, *the promised land*) V.V. Vinogradov. *Russian language. Grammatical doctrine of the word* / V.V. Vinogradov. - M.: Higher. school, 1986. - p. 137..

A lot of phraseological units came from ancient mythological literature (*Augean stables*, *Achilles' heel*, *sword of Damocles*, *Prometheus fire*, *tantalum torment*).

Sometimes borrowed phraseological units are used without translation: *alma mater* (lat. mother-nurse); *tabula rasa*

(lat. clean board; something untouched, absolutely clean).

The source of the original phraseology is turns from the works of writers: happy hours are not observed (A. Griboyedov); affairs of bygone days (A. Pushkin); and the casket just opened (I. Krylov); knight for an hour (N. Nekrasov); living corpse (L. Tolstoy); a man in a case (A. Chekhov); Man - that sounds proud! (M. Gorky)

Such set expressions from fiction and journalism are usually called winged expressions.

Phraseologisms are almost always bright, figurative expressions. Therefore, they are an important expressive means of language used by writers as ready-made figurative definitions, comparisons, as emotional and pictorial characteristics of heroes, the surrounding reality, etc.

For example, K. Paustovsky in the novel "Smoke of the Fatherland", characterizing the action of one of the heroes, instead of words, without hesitation, thoughtlessly uses phraseologism headlong: She was attracted to him by childishness, a

tendency to get carried away headlong, chivalry, an ironic attitude towards himself.

A. Sitkovsky's poem "All the best that exists in the world" is built on the use of phraseological turns. Or N. Gogol in "Dead Souls": I believe, for my part, in all honesty: eight hryvnia per soul, this is the reddest price I. Ilf and E. Petrov in the novel "The Twelve Chairs" give a whole synonymous series phraseological units with the meanings "to die": "Klavdia Ivanovna died," the customer said. "Well, the kingdom of heaven," agreed Bezenchuk. "It means that the old woman has passed away... Old women, they always pass away... Or they give their souls to God, depending on what kind of old woman it is." Yours, for example, is small and in the body, which means it has passed away. And for example, which is larger and thinner - it is believed that she gives her soul to God "... Larin B.A. Essays on phraseology // History of the Russian language and general linguistics. - M., 1977. - S. 51.

Sometimes writers use phraseological units in a modified, re-arranged form. In these cases phraseologism acquires

new aesthetic qualities. For example, M. Saltykov-Shchedrin uses the phraseologism to poke his nose somewhere, expanding it: Censorship is used to sticking its stinking nose into the very sanctuary of the writer's thought.

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